

INCLINATION CATEGORY IN UZBEK, RUSSIAN AND KARAKALPAK LANGUAGES

Usanova Qademay Muratbay qizi

Nukus State Pedagogical Institute named after Ajiniyaz
The Faculty of Turkic languages is a student of
Uzbek language direction 2 in foreign language groups.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11145774>

Abstract. In this article, the comparison of the verb word category in Uzbek, Russian and Karakalpak languages, the category of declension in verbs, the command declension, their alternatives in Russian and Karakalpak languages, similarities and differences were studied.

Keywords: verb, mile category, command, precision, condition, grammar, affix, present tense, respect, plural, please, advice, next tense, adjective, majhul ratio, past tense.

Verb-the richest in grammatical categories in all 3 languages, grammatical nature is the most complex category. Words belonging to the verb word category indicate the process.

The action, state meaning of a verb is expressed through its special grammatical categories. The verb has grammatical categories like rank – zalog – da'reje, mile – naklonenie – meyl, tense – Vremya – Ma'ha'l, person and son – liso I chislo – bet Ha'm san in all 3 languages.

The verb stands out among all word categories in terms of its versatility in meaning, its richness in grammatical categories, forms, as well as its most important place in the composition of the sentence. The Russian linguist academician Peshkovsky was certainly right when he said: "when word categories are compared to planets, the verb is the sun among them." The use of the verb as a central clause in Uzbek also proves this¹.

In Uzbek, Russian and Karakalpak languages, the miles category of the verb word category indicates the attitude of work-movement towards real reality. Every 3 languages also have 5 different types of miles, such as the command buyruq mayli – buyruq mayli – повелительное наклонение – buyriq meyl, aniqlik mayli – изъявительное наклонение – aniqliq meyl, shart mayli – условное наклонение – sha'rt meyl, Karakalpak again tilek inclination and maqset inclination.

In Uzbek, the condition May is made by adding the affix –sa to the verb base, after which the person-number affix is added. Person III does not have a person-number affix, while Person III plural –s affix is added². For example: in unity: summer-sa-m, summer-sa-ng, summer-sa; in plural: summer-sa-k, summer-sa-ngiz, summer-sa-lar. The meaning of the Uzbek term May is expressed in Russian by the combination of the word Esli or kogda with the verb in the next tense form. For example: if you come to ours tomorrow, we will prepare a lesson together. - Esli Ti zavtra pridesh K Nam, budem vmeste gotovit uroki.

The conditional declension of the verb in Russian – uslovnnoe naklonenie-forms denotes a desire, an opportunity that is fulfilled when a marked condition is made. That is why they are used in the sense of 2: condition and desire. When the condition is applied in M'no, such

¹ Muhiddinova X va boshqalar. Hozirgi o'zbek adabiy tili. Toshkent. 2006. – B. 110.

² Azizov O. va boshqalar. O'zbek va rus tillarining qiyosiy grammatikasi Toshkent, 1965. – B. 61.

verbs denote that the condition of the sign-level of the work-action can be realized. For example: *ya vibrat bi druguyu, kogda Bi Ya bil, Kak Ti poet* (a. S. Pushkin). – I wanted another, if I were such a poet. In Russian, when conditional miles are applied in the sense of desire, it means that work-action is not in reality, it is only the desire of the speaker. For example: *ya volkom bi vigriz bureaucracy* (V. V. Mayakovsky). – As if I were gnawing at bureaucracies.

The conditional *mayli-Sha'rt meyili*-form in Karakalpak language denotes the condition for the functioning or non-functioning of the binary -action and is made through the addition of the affixes *-sa/ - se* to the verb base and stands in 3 persons, singular and plural. For example: singular: *alsam, alsan'*, *alsa*; plural: *alsaq, Alsan'iz*, like *alsa*.

In Uzbek, a command *May* is the base of verbs that do not take a *mile*, a tense person-number affix, equivalent to a form with a verb's 2 person Command form. In this, meanings such as *buryuk* and *please* are expressed³. For example: *ol, summer, wish, come, give, Come, Go, arrow, work, come, stand up, dress up*. The person II command form is sometimes formed by adding the affix *-gin, - kin, - qin*. For example: *take, write, read like*. In this case, the meaning of the advice prevails over the command. The honorific meaning is formed by adding the affix *-ng (-ing)* to the verb base. For example: *take, write, go, see, sit like*. The plural form is represented by the affixes *-ngiz, -*. For example: *like your summer, your presence, Your Work, Your Arrow*.

In Russian, the command *may-povelitelnie naklonenie* –the 2nd person singular form of the command verb is made primarily by adding *-I, - Y, or -Ь* to the base of the present tense verb. For example: *pish-ut – pishi, Khod-Yat – Khodi, rabota-Yut – rabotay, Gulya-Yut – gulyay abi*. Honorific and plural forms are made with the addition of the suffix *-TE* to the singular form. For example: *like pishi – pishite, gulyay – gulyayte, vstan – vstante*. When a command form is made from the present tense base of one-syllable verbs, the vowel *e* is usually acquired. For example: *pyut – Pei, lyut – Lei*.

In Karakalpak, the command *mile* – the *kidney MEIL*-is mainly indicated through person II and person III. For example: *al, say, oqit, jazdir, U'yret, U'yren, oqin', say'*, like *oqisin*. The command *May* is formed by adding A II-person suffix to the verb base, such as *(-i)-n'iz/(-i) - n'iz*⁴. For example: the affix *-sin/-sin* is used in person III in the singular of the order declension. As well as being the basic form of the affix command *mile*, it also comes as the person-number form of the command *mile* in person III. At the same time, this form is uniform for the number of units and multiples of the order *mile* III person. For example: *let Ol say – let ol say*. The command has the plural form *-(a)yiq/-(e)yik* of the first number of miles. This uniform is N. K. Dmitriev, in his "grammar of the Bashkir language", takes the wish from the plural *Foma* of the I Person of the *mile* and conditionally transfers the order to the i person, plural form of the *mile*⁵.

The definite article in Uzbek-*iz'yavitelnoe naklonenie* in Russian – *aniqliq meyli* in Karakalpak – clearly expresses whether or not the movement will be *voqe* in one of the 3 tenses. In Uzbek, Russian and Karakalpak languages, the difference in the accuracy *mile* is that

³Azizov O. va boshqalar. O'zbek va rus tillarining qiyosiy grammatikasi Toshkent, 1965. – B. 59.

⁴Da'wletov A va boshqalar. Ha'zirgi qaraqalpaq a'debiy tili. – No'kis, 2010. – B. 150.

⁵Dmitriev N. K. Boshqort telenen' grammatikahi. - Leningrad, 1950. – B. 174.

in Uzbek and Karakalpak languages there are several forms of each tense. The Russian language, on the other hand, is not very rich in modern forms.

In place of the conclusion, we must say that the verb word category is a word category that is distinguished from each other by very large differences, even if it represents the meaning of action and posture in all 3 languages. We have briefly compared the type category of the verb word category below. We looked at the opposite sides of each other. Learning languages by analogy will be easy and fun for any language learner. It is sure to increase, of course, even the craving for language learning.

References:

1. Azizov O va boshqalar. O'zbek va rus tillarining qiyosiy grammatikasi Toshkent: "O'qituvchi" nashriyoti.1965.
2. O.Azizov va boshqalar. O'zbek va rus tillarining qiyosiy grammatikasi. Toshkent: "O'qituvchi" nashriyoti. 1986.
3. Bekbergenov A. Rus ha'm qaraqalpaq tillerinin' salistirmali grammatikasi. No'kis: "Bilim" nashriyoti. 2006
4. Da'wletov A va boshqalar Ha'zirgi qaraqalpaq a'debiy tili. No'kis: "Bilim" nashriyoti. 2010.
5. Muhiddinova X va boshqalar. Hozirgi o'zbek adabiy tili. Toshkent: "O'qituvchi" nashriyoti. 2006.